

MIMS 2.2.5.1 - Change Theory

What are the Yi, mytho-historically, and in the context of the “Big G” framework (particularly Physics), and what can we do to use them to fix and enhance STEMM, and our human and natural world?

May 2022

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM
Lexington, KY

ABSTRACT

The ancient Chinese, from Fuxi (mythical leader) through the Confucians, were very attentive to the changing phenomenon around them, and reduced them down to the Changes (Yi, 易). There are 64 listed in the “I Ching” or “Zhouyi”; one for each DNA codon? But in the end, the result is a massive combination of possibilities, between 385 and 1.27×10^{89} possibilities, depending on your perspective. But there are other potential uses for the Changes, and in the end, our interest is solely about creating, using, and extending the MIMS philosophy for the purposes of improving mankind and the planet we live on.

Key Words: I Ching - hexagram - MIMS - Operations Research - Creativity - AI - Quantum mechanics

EPEMC :: Philosophy
Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

Review - the Model of MIMS	3
Mimsical Native Ideals, Yellowstone and Kentucky in Retrospective	3
The MIMS of Creativity	4
Conformity, Fidelity, Following, Guiding, & Enriching	5
Conformity	5
Fidelity	6
Following	6
Guiding	7
Enrich(en)ing	7
Benefit & Blessings	8
Fortune, Æther, Dætherial Evidence	8
Operations Research - a science 100% MIMS compliant	9
Data Analytics	11
Game Theory	12
Change Theory	13
AI and Analog Computation to Simulate Quantum Fluctuations in the PPPC	14
Table 1 - AI Robots/Androids, date comparison	15
Procedurally Generated AI meets Proof of Power	15
New QED+EHD	17
Simulating Natural Systems with Enhanced Mechanics, and QEHD	18
Applying Change Theory as an Operations Research using QEHD	19
Conclusions	20
References	21

Review - the Model of MIMS

The reader will recall from the MIMS 1.0 paper¹ that a hypothetical model of the MIMS, was that of a simple pairing of yang and yin, in a particular order: a gua 卦 (trigram), which was the fundamental stepping stone for (Yijing) or Book of Changes, so this is a layer between the Dao or (Power²), and the trigram Laws (*P* Power), of which there are eight. This bilayer, as it were, is reflective of cellular membranous formation, and is confirmed in many ways. Nevertheless, let us briefly re-describe the situation. We have an ætheric [or dætheric] (*A+N* Powers) model which enables us to describe some form of energy-mass or **charge** exchange in from the materia-stratum to the invisible realms of space, æther, and counterspace (SCS). These topics are covered elsewhere. What is important, is that we see that the Heaven or Yang is above and the Earth or Yin is below, but “as above so below” these are ONE, and thus we have Genesis, “Let Us make Man(kind) in Our image, in male and female He made them.”³ The He here is not a man but a yang 陽 or unified (whole) presentation of the entire Order. Dao 道 over Hundun 混沌 (Chaos). The Creative Force 乾 gives energy to the Created/Receptive 坤, but the energy of the Void (Wuji, 无极) percolates upward (via a form of ;’evaporation’) to the Creative. This circulatory effect constitutes the basis or model for the self-consistent MIMS hypothesis and philosophical construct of a MIMS; MIMS itself is a MIMS.

This is not quite
the I Ching
Force-flow (F

Mimsical Native Ideals, Yellowstone and Kentucky in Retrospective

In order to understand the concepts of non-linear dynamics, it might serve us very well to remember how *choice* of behavior does, indeed, affect the outcomes. In other words: philosophy matters.

In this case we can see not one, but two (granted, rare? examples of Native fengshui 風水 perfection) examples of ‘perfect’ mimisification of land & ecosystems. Yellowstone and Kentucky (Kithiki) were both “happy hunting grounds” for the tribes that entered into them, and were absolutely 100% maintained. In particular, the predator populations were respected, and the forests were control-burned. There are, therefore, shocking results caused by the sudden removal of these ideal, but real, management practices. In Yellowstone National Park, the first of its kind, predators were exterminated and plant and herd populations were decimated. In Kentucky the situation was much worse, the trees were clear cut during the pig iron furnace era, then later there were lumber industries and coal mining destruction. The effect was to completely destroy the bison, elk, wolf, and panther populations, among other damage.

1

https://www.academia.edu/50300514/On_the_Membranous_Interface_of_the_Material_and_the_Spiritual_from_an_EPEMC_perspective_and_Dual_Double_Layer_Economics_a_proposed_test_of_EPEMCs_metallic_properties_tensile_strength_malleability_durability

2

http://www.academia.edu/53271235/Explication_of_the_Versatility_of_the_Big_G_diagram_in_MIMS_1_0

³ Genesis 1:26

Consequently, within 2 generations the ecosystem was destroyed, as is detailed in “How the West Was Lost.”⁴

So what does this tell us? It tells us that **not all changes are from the Changes**, and in fact, human beliefs and behaviors matter, quite a bit.

Native Americans understood this, as did the Chinese, the Buddhists, and many others. In our society, consequence is being replaced with Orwellian lies and distortions of reality. This is highly dangerous, to start with, and from there it may, in fact, mean a total loss of progress due to misalignment and **no cohesion** to Reality.

The problem is, not only that we ignored the native Way, politically, racially, socially, etc. Obviously all cultures have positives and negatives, even profound or ‘savage’ ones. But they have things that aid humans to benefit. In some, wiser, older societies they have ways of preventing violence and incest by *encouraging* adultery. However, the fact remains that the natives clearly found means and ways to manage the “happy hunting grounds” which were MIMSically much more solid than our own monocultural agriculture. And the failure to utilize these is not an example of the “Changes” as a force (i.e., ‘climate change’) but human ignorance, or nescience, even stupidity. Or maybe, P.O.S. behavior⁵ which cannot and should not be tolerated any longer. But that is a story for another time.

Let us then discuss what Michael Crichton described in “Sphere”⁶ as the *one power* that makes mankind, and sentients, different from all other beings. That aspect of us is **imagination**, and its MIMS is “creativity.” Let us also stay creative as well as critically think, so that we may keep the “landscape” clean and beautiful, too. That might require some selective hunting and controlled burning! But the forest *and the tree*, both will matter. We will try not to miss one for the other.

The MIMS of Creativity

Creativity is defined as “the use of the imagination or original ideas, especially in the production of an artistic work.” It is not clear that art is the best representation, or only a single, good representation. Where is the data? However, it is clear that the definition means that Creativity is a form of psychological tool. Why does it work? In MIMS 2.0 the author provided six hypotheses⁷, one of which was that “more ideas - good or bad - lead to more good ideas and more solutions”, and that this was essential to a MIMS (based upon the work of Thomas Edison). Therefore, the imaginative capacity, utilized in a flow of creative (or artistic, sure) output, leads to the free and uninhibited expression of more and more ideas, ergo more good ideas and solutions (especially in engineering), which, of course improves life.

However, the author wishes to modulate this with caution. We see that life is full of contraction, compression, and limitation. Therefore, we do not see an endless amplified signal of Creativity, but a standing wave. Its outer frequency modulation very well might be the yearly cycle of seasons, or economic cycles, or political and religious cycles, or Earthly and cosmic cycles (such as

⁴ <https://www.amazon.com/How-West-Was-Lost-Transformation/dp/080185296X/>

⁵ https://www.academia.edu/77592483/MIMS_2_83_POS_Theory

⁶ <https://www.amazon.com/Sphere-Michael-Crichton/dp/0061990558/>

⁷ https://www.academia.edu/50804855/MIMS_2_Applications_discussions

EPEMC :: Philosophy
Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

sunspots). Or, it may be that the outer frequency is the Changes, or perhaps the Changes are amalgamations of the above (and forces such as market forces, meteorology, electrogeology, etc.)

But whatever it is, there appears to be a *standing wave*⁸ of creativity, output, testing, and riddance of ideas, which are possibly good or possibly bad (probably bad, actually). This might even be affected by the “arc of opportunity” or be an indication of said arc, we do not really know. So many opportunities come from pure creative spaces, and yet so many come from intuitive flashes or happenstance, coincidence, “luck”, and the general sense of “as it happens of itself.” Yet, on some level we sense, and perhaps could measure, the rate of expansion and contraction of the opportunities and the successes or failures of Creativity.

What can we deduce and educe about Creativity as a MIMS from this? It is a tool with which we must bear in mind, with patience, the facts of the Parable of the Sower⁹: most of the seed will fall on stony ground, or be choked by thorns, eaten by birds, and dried out in the sun. Most of it will fail. That is not necessarily of our making, except whereby our Creativity does not match the Changes. Is this really the source of “Heaven’s Will” (tianyi, 天意) and not an actual force expression of “God’s Love” or “Grace” or other energy wave descending “from On High”? Again, where is the data? We need data for the waveforms, and we need data for the force expressions, as well as calendrical data to compare with our insights of Changes vis-a-vis weather, stock market, solar wind/sunspots, etc. We need to compare with average injury rates, psychological “beatdowns” of life, monetary affectations, to even begin to understand if there is a correlation to our Creative output, input, and efficacy.

Conformity, Fidelity, Following, Guiding, & Enriching

When we talk about Creativity, however, there are a few facets which do seem to *adhere* to the “effort” (work over time = power) and enable it to succeed, and these are known from the “I Ching” itself, or from alchemy, in general. It is impossible to describe all of the alchemical furnace workings here, so please consult the “Threefold Sciences”¹⁰ for more details. In general, these five “tuning forks” should get the user or *Mimsifier*¹¹ or “faturizer” engaged with the Changes and Change Theory, for robust application.

Conformity

It may seem, at first, unusual to talk about rigid conformity in the context of Creativity. In fact, though, it is the most natural learning act in the world. People learn to play jazz only after they know the music sheet and notes. They learn to sculpt after they learn to paint, build, or do carpentry, welding, etc. They learn to design only after classes and mentorship, even degrees. Etc. To have a S.Y.S.T.E.M.¹² is incredibly valuable, because above all Tianyi *demands* obedience. “Be still and know that I am the Lord, thy God.” and “Open thy mouth that I shall fill thy belly.”

⁸ <https://www.britannica.com/science/standing-wave-physics>

⁹ Matthew 13

¹⁰ <https://bit.ly/3lsecCl>

¹¹ a) One who consciously uses MIMS to improve the future.; b) one who purposefully creates MIMS.

¹² Save Your Self Time, Energy, and Money

EPEMC :: Philosophy
Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

Religions fail when people corrupt themselves and others. They help spirituality when they guide the newcomer along the Changes to predestined, and well understood, psychological journeys that overcome disasters and dangers (“Pitfalls” in the “I Ching” 易經).

Conformity appears to work because “Fire” 離 (the Clinging), is associated not only with enlightenment and plasma/PEM, but also with the Lord and even Heaven. Granted these are separate powers, but in some senses they are the same, and the canvas in which mankind first understood the PEMF¹³ (*F* power) was the Plasma-electromagnetic Sky¹⁴ or “heavens” as we still call them. In fact, the mediation of the Spheres of Heaven with the Spheres of Earth is this membranous crust we live upon which is “neutral” to a degree (neglecting telluric currents and leylines), but is an excellent chemical soup, so to speak. There is much that occurs in this meeting place, and it reflects - exactly - our diagram for a MIMS (see Figure 1). The coincidence of this has to be very low. Unfortunately with only one planet with known life and very little details of other planets’ geological interiors (beyond mere guesses and conjecture), we cannot prove this theory, at this time. We can only say there is a very strong correlation between the PEMS/HEGEME axis and the mediation of the *L+F+A* powers, beyond the utilization of the Force in the former, and the relationship of fields in the latter. But it can be definitely said, studying history and the words of witnesses and sages of the times that *defying* Tianyi has always been disastrous, and at times using Tianyi has appeared highly advantageous, even to the point of insurance. However, the data is macrocytic, not microscopic. There are even examples of *forging* conforming to Tianyi which have also worked¹⁵!

Fidelity

By contrast, fidelity is a matter of loyalty, that is *choosing*, to conform to the Force, the Powers, Heaven et al. It is a matter of trying to match its behaviors, to make oneself as patient and giving, untiring and ‘magnanimous’ (as the Confucians put it) as Heaven and Earth. Not just the Spheres of these, but the very energy fields and strictures or *gua* and their Laws (Causation and Vibration, respectively). To obey these, but subconsciously, is a matter of Fidelity. With conformity you do by obeying. With Fidelity you choose to match. It’s an honor.

Following

Following is similar, except that it is also obeisant, like conformity. But following does not have the authority to make any choice. Following means that you look to the leader and you give way. Not because you can do nothing else, like a slave. But you willingly give it. In which case, you are at the whims of the Power that flows down to you.

¹³ Plasma-electromagnetic Force, i.e. the Unified Æther Field:

https://www.academia.edu/37439506/Magnetic_Universe_Theory_A_Top_Down_Review_of_Phases_of_Magnetic_Theory_Development_with_accompanying_historiography_and_comparison_with_Unified_Æther_Field_Theories_including_EPEMC

¹⁴

https://www.academia.edu/36753643/Our_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Sky_Application_of_Hollow_Expanding_Growing_Electromagnetic_Earth_Hypothesis_with_particular_respect_to_the_Earths_Atmosphere_starting_from_the_Lithosphere_and_ascending_Altitude

¹⁵ In particular the story of ^ letting loose his hair and *acting* possessed of Xuanwu (Leigong, the Thunder/Sky god) to win the battle and take control of the Han Dynasty, comes to mind.

Guiding

Guiding is the precise opposite. It means that you have followers, and you lead them along. In such a situation, it is important to use an admixture of the previous three, in the proper ratio, to control others and self (ego) by domination with the Changes and Laws of God. It is not an easy path, and people will buck and some will fight it. Others will present challenges, many of which cannot easily be overcome. In which case, there is not much you can do but sigh in those situations, if your lot is to guide and teach even when others don't want to conform, or have Fidelity themselves, much less follow. In such a case, the author has found himself, and it is absolutely the most difficult of these five. However, Guiding means to be strong via being vulnerable, and to be strong by being stoic, and there is an alternation of these, and with honor and not anger, which will yield a great result that is not to be had by tyrants and others. As for those that lack fidelity and are bad at following, they reap very bad karma and Changes, because it is a sin - apparently - to not follow the leader. It is most easy to see this in Exodus, with the difficulties Moshe (Moses) had to go through with the Hebrews and various shared responsibilities. They did not always listen or respect his God-given authority, and sometimes it was a great pain to him.

In the end the leader guides not for the sake of power, but for the sake of Love. The rabble or masses will never understand that. Not until trouble comes. And then, as was said by Admiral Ernest King in World War II, *"When trouble comes, they send for the Sons of Bitches."*

Enrich(en)ing

The issue with what alchemists call "working the furnace" and "cooking the medicine" is really a matter of enriching (or for artists: beautifying) the material stratum. This is a matter of advancing the project, person, event, or situation (some type of object) to a place of greatness... and then surpassing that.

It has this to do with the Changes: it is a matter of timing as to when to advance, and then when to "stop the firing" and "cull the medicine" before "the medicine is burned." The author has also made the mistake of applying excessive voltage, or amperage, to an admixture. It's the mistake of youth (which I Ching calls "Youthful Folly"), and it can really ruin that which was grown or created. In such a situation one "Works on What's Been Spoiled." which apparently comes from Wind/Flux beneath the Mountain/Conservation, and leads to "rotting of the vegetables."

Bear in mind that while the author has used in another work, the analogy of making your own salad at the buffet, to describe enriching and how it is enriching to the point of absolute delectability... there is no point at which if the vegetables spoil that the admixture can be further enriched. At that point the rotted veggies have to be returned to the soil, and after which new things can grow. That process is guided by "Waiting" (another Change). And has nothing to do with our present interests. One can, and should, of course study all of the Changes. But these five energies will represent our main five elemental ways of dealing with the MIMS of Change Theory:

Conformity (Fire) | Fidelity (Wood) | Following (Water) | Guiding (Metal) | Enriching (Earth)

Benefit & Blessings

One of the main interests of the Chinese in their pseudoscience of fengshui, and in geomancy and fortune telling, etc. is the almost obsequious or felicitous reception of Benefit and Blessings. This goes from the burning of money and placing golden cats in corners all the way to oracles and omens, and eventually even to magick or even black magick practices. But the results promised in Quanzhen 全真 (Complete Reality) or Longmen 龍門 (Dragon gate) Taoism is different: it is that by conforming in one of the main five ways to the Dao, one will escape the “Pitfalls” (another hexagram), and in so doing find the only true freedom: acceptance of ‘God’s Will’ in our lives. This Will has been expressed many ways by many cultures, and we won’t push for a Christian [only] or other ethos here. However, the existence of God is already dealt with elsewhere¹⁶, and will be treated as it is: a mathematical, information, and mytho-historical fact.

In the attainment of blessings, however, it is *not* clear, i.e. transparent, that you must be a believer to receive them. For example the Chinese say that Heaven bestows rain upon the good and criminal alike. It is also true that every man, good or evil, has a mother. That mothers are not always a benefit (believe him the author knows this well) is not relevant to the Chinese idea. It is that everyone gets X% of fortune, Y% of luck/blessing, and Z% of opportunity to make it happen. It doesn’t seem that “God’s Love” (whatever that *is*, which is also not clear, so it has been termed *agape*¹⁷ by the Greeks, and set aside) depends wholly on worship, belief, acceptance, or even action! But acknowledgement, and proper position (shi 勢) appears to relate directly to **punishment** and discipline! How quaint. This sounds mostly like our description of Law and Justice. The irony is that Nature and God’s justice and laws work almost nothing like our own. But that’s a discussion... for another time.

Fortune, Æther, Dætherial Evidence

In the discussions of fortune, the Æther and Dæther¹⁸ evidence has been mentioned before, and provided in previous works on crypto and finance, etc. It is not essential to cover all of it again here, only to mention thus far our interests have laid along these lines:

- Money
- Luck or at least “good results”
- Cryptocurrency
- Data Leylines¹⁹
- Dual Layer Economics²⁰
- Fibonacci Pressure²¹

So what is it that we need to discuss in the application of Change Theory? Really only this: theoretically *if* one ‘conforms to the Changes’ and *if* one even uses them, with or without understanding, but probably more so with understanding, and *if* one obtains Heaven’s “favor”,

¹⁶ Ibid.

¹⁷ https://www.academia.edu/50357891/MIMS_and_Shi

¹⁸ https://www.academia.edu/67236577/MIMS_2_102_In_pursuit_of_the_Dæther

¹⁹ “Dæther” Ibid. pp. 4, 13-16

²⁰ “MIMS 1.0” Ibid. pp. 15

²¹ https://www.academia.edu/67387410/MIMS_2_1_212a_Fibonacci_Pressure etc.

EPEMC :: Philosophy
Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

whatever that means and *if* there is an Æther (let alone Dæther) and *if* there is any possibility that these things are true and real or measurable (data and evidence; ie. empiricism), *then* it goes without saying that to not fund research, let alone technology, into the achievement of these things for the attainment of benefit is anathema and probably extremely troglodytic. Maybe, even barbaric. For example the factual existence of the Human Flesh Industry²² and its reliance on black magick, blood magick, and pseudoscientific Scientism surrounding various ideas from immortality to transmutation and transhumanism (not transgenderism, that is more of a Strategy²³ and National Security discussion) would constitute forms of barbarism that would likely then be considered heinous by most people, and perhaps other sentients. For example, setting aside angels and spirits and the like, what would aliens think if they saw our current behavior? What would they think about the infanticide, eugenics, animal mutilations, etc.? Clearly they would be concerned that we had lost our minds. They'd be right (if they themselves weren't the causes of it). Moreover, if no one explained simply, and matter of factly, that this was all the results of the Exodus cataclysms and the failure to eradicate barbarism, such as heart sacrifice, cannibalism, ritual headhunting, etc. then one would expect them to be highly perplexed. Even mortified.

They'd probably be very concerned about our paranoia regarding insectoids, planet destruction, weapons of the Gods, symbolism, secret societies, chronic habitual lying and a commercial injustice system, Satanism, witchcraft or other superstitious behaviors, particle obsession and smashing, pollution, airborne disease manufacture ("gain of function"), aerosol particulate manufacture²⁴ and spread²⁵, climate change hysteria and cultism, political occultism, Scientism and various intense P.O.S. behaviors regarding the perversion of logic and empiricism, including Orwellianism, and more. That list is enough to make anyone, indeed even an autistic billionaire, off this rock to leave for a dead planet with no people (Mars)!

It is enough to wonder about why to repeat three World Wars, just to satisfy the whims of eugenicist-Nazi families²⁶ and fulfill their hopes of depopulation agendas and the creation of a robot mediated neo-feudal technocratic oligarchy, wherein the common classes are mere chattel... and now we have this sort of intense hatred among political classes, and the rebirth of tribalistic prejudice. The return of socialism, and the resurgence of war, now corporatized, with fascist overtones and neo-religious undertones.

Operations Research - a science 100% MIMS compliant

In World War II, America responded to an attack and a growing assertion (politically and socially) that we needed to intervene, again, into European affairs to deal with the Third Reich and Hitler. Plenty of propaganda for the war effort was being produced between 1939 and 1941 to bring this assertion to relevance, even without discussing conspiracy theories about Pearl

²² Abortion for fetal cell harvest, cannibalism, human slavery market, organ harvesting, child porn economy...

²³ https://www.academia.edu/51643169/MIMS_2_6_2_Strategy_and_Dualism

²⁴ https://www.academia.edu/74466574/The_Peer_Review_Cult_cover_up_Conspiracy_Facts_the_fact_checkers_do_not_want_you_to_know_about

²⁵ https://www.geoengineeringmonitor.org/2021/02/stratospheric_aerosol_injection

²⁶ Bush, Ford, Rockefeller, etc.

EPEMC :: Philosophy
Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

Harbor²⁷. The fact is that the United States of America, the world's most militant empire since the British or Romans or Mongols, then went into motion and as it was put by one Japanese Admiral, a "sleeping giant has been awakened and filled with terrible resolve."

From that war effort came an entire science, centered around data, logistics, and project management. It was called Operations Research²⁸ (O.R.²⁹) and it was, at first, not computerized. However in the 1950s and 1960s, attempts at Game Theory³⁰ or Queuing Theory³¹, etc. went from mathematical theory into computerized experiment. 80 years later, the field of "Data Analytics"³² has been thriving ever since, and only getting stronger.

Setting aside whether or not the Internet, and especially Social Media, is an anti-MIMS, or even a threat to human or national security due to factors relating to the Force, waves, multiverse theory, etc., not to mention the immorality and threat to kids pervasive on it... there is a strengthening effect to OR and DA that comes from the Internet's inherent data basis. This leaves us to see that OR itself, with its goal of improving human life and solving problems is itself 100% MIMS compliant³³. It is potentially infinite, with a finite overall structure or process, it promotes many ideas, it follows the Scientific Method³⁴, it is creative, etc. We do not need to list out every hypothesis especially given that every hypothesis about MIMS philosophy is not even yet known!

So we must ask ourselves... should OR and DA be Change Theory compliant? Should they be OR/DA_CT? And, in a way, shouldn't all MIMS applications? Should they or should they not conform to the Changes?

The Nei Yeh, the world's 2nd oldest Taoist text extant after the "12-sided Jade Knob"³⁵ says the following:

*"Daily we make use of its inner power (Te).
The Way (Tao) is what infuses the body,
Yet people are unable to fix it in place.
It goes forth but does not return,
It comes back but does not stay.*

***The Way has no fixed position;
It abides within the excellent mind.
When the mind is tranquil and the vital breath is regular,
The Way can thereby be halted.
Cultivate your mind, make your thoughts tranquil,***

²⁷ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Pearl-Harbor-and-the-back-door-to-war-theory-1688287>

²⁸ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/operations-research/History>

²⁹ <https://www.informs.org/Explore/History-of-O.R.-Excellence/Bibliographies/The-Origins-of-OR>

³⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Game_theory

³¹ <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/q/queuing-theory.asp>

³² <https://www.mastersindatascience.org/learning/what-is-data-analytics/>

³³ https://www.academia.edu/65563310/MIMS_1_01_03_Philosophy_Integration_Self_test

³⁴ MIMS 2.0, Ibid, pp. 5-6

³⁵ *"The Genuine Ones of old: Their sleep was without dreams, Their waking was without cares, Their eating was without sweetness, Their breathing was deeply deep. The breathing of the Genuine is from their heels. The breathing of the multitude is from their throats. The submissive talk in gulps as though retching. In those whose desires are deep, the dynamism of Heaven is shallow."*

And the Way can thereby be attained.

As for the Way:

When people lose it they die;

When people gain it they flourish.

When endeavors lose it they fail;

When they gain it they succeed.

*For the heavens, the ruling principle is to be **aligned**.*

For the earth, the ruling principle is to be level.

For human beings the ruling principle is to be tranquil.

Therefore, the Sage:

Alters with the seasons but doesn't falter,

Shifts with things but doesn't change places with them.³⁶

Data Analytics

In particular, the author is most excited about the concepts of OR in the field of Data Analytics, as they may directly pertain to the issue of dætherial mechanics (proposed). If the reader shall recall, the author hypothesized that data itself might be found in an æther stratum of particular connection (non-MIMSical) between the *A* and *N* domains or spheres of power. If this is true, and it is a non-MIMSical stratum (unreal barrier), then perhaps there is a “quantum foam” access to it, as there is for the proposed (by mainstream Quantum Mechanics) Void/0 point/SCS³⁷. If this is true, and if we hold the Law of Conservation (*P* domain) to be the holder of the *A* power's Source-keys (generally called the Akashic³⁸ by New Age mystics), then perhaps certain “records” or futurization technologies can/may exist. If this is so, should not the *N* power (data for this evidence) be the particular means of which to attract this information?

Furthermore, based upon weather and stock market (considered semi-Chaotic systems) modeling, it seems there is great \$\$³⁹ value in this type of research, and work, and furthermore Big Data in general might be affected. After all, there is a known memory decay rate for all media, even crystal, and there is probably a known decay rate for data. People change, believe it or not, and while morality (as has been shown) makes perhaps a better weapon than a MIMS, and one can ‘whack’ others on the head with old, now irrelevant data, it is probably anti-MIMSical to do so based upon cancel/cancer culture and the destructive lies of #metoo. In fact, the entire disease of cultural socialism or cultural marxism rests upon the delight of delayed outrage from old data. But it always seems incredibly phony and definitely politically malevolent, no matter who does it. Therefore, there might be something to the idea that old data “rots” like the aforementioned vegetation analogy. It might very well be that what keeps us from **enrichening** our society is that the “sweet life” or “good life” has to rotate through a rotting

³⁶ Selections, “Original Tao”

<https://www.amazon.com/Original-Tao-Foundations-Mysticism-Translations/dp/0231115652/>

³⁷ Spongey Counterspace

³⁸ https://karolinum.cz/data/clanek/8423/CEJCR_3_2_0109.pdf

³⁹ https://www.academia.edu/76140647/MIMS_Æther_Flow_and_Business_Circuit_Theory , pp.17-18

period. The Chinese doctors insisted that sweetness rots and spoils. Might the “American Dream” turn into the “American Nightmare” all too soon from excessive militarization (War being the pre-eminent anti-MIMS), fascism (government is without a doubt the worst MIMS ever made), and social self-cannibalization? It very well might. It might be that all enriching is impossible, too, if daughter mechanics is the MIMS we have little prospect of currently development and “mining” or “accessing” or “harvesting” because we have no major initiatives for funding, research, etc. of Change Theory! Imagine, if the Law of Evolutionary-Flux (Wind gua, 巽) governs the physics of the Æther, and it sits opposite of the Abyss gua, 坎 (Law of Relativity) to the Law of Conservation (Mountain gua, 艮), then isn't it likely that the slight relational differences of these Laws (which are really one Law), might be the matter of life and death understanding for **all ætherial mechanics**. Not data/information alone. It might govern spiritual mechanics, luck mechanics, fortune mechanics, chronology mechanics... it might be the hidden crux that defines how OR/DA works *or usually does not work*.

Some would say only the *what* matters, and not the why. In my experience the “why” gives us leverage into the eddies of the current - laminar or turbulent - that the what is experiencing as *how*. And how things work is highly valuable. There are whole books, channels, DIY networks and shows devoted to how. “How” is so incredibly valuable, there are fields of engineering and science devoted to it extensively, such as chemical and materials engineering. Therefore if there are eddies of “tricks” or “hacks” into reality which can be data processed by simply analyzing data via thermodynamic and aerodynamic or even plasma-gaseous mechanics, such as “Fibonacci Pressure”, shouldn't we divest into this?

Game Theory

In terms of game theory, we do not here mean the OR field, but actually utilizing play, particularly multi-person (akin to multi-AI) play, to turn neurological processing, and intuitive or quantum computing brain activity into results gathering. It is the author's experience that the brain and its nervous system interface, can actually interact with others' bodies, inanimate objects, and even digital images and media. There is some evidence of this as well in subconscious or heart responses involving Internet news and images. Moreover, it is well known that imagery in general (a conveyance of data) affects the psyche. If this is true, why not vice versa? Cannot the mind *will* things to happen, or make a strong assertion - via fear or reverie - into a particular quantum data stream? Cannot criminals be created as well as make the choice for themselves? Can we not pigeon-hole others and affect their entire life streams? Is there a form of mentalist magick that alters the **tangible, life results** of others? Is there some data field for the storage of mental refuse, or “sin”? Is there some way that our “karmic debts” are stored... in a field in or around the person? If chakras are electromagnetic or Æther/PEMF spiral vortices centered around glands and nerve plexuses, and we can measure these with our own “mirror neurons”⁴⁰ (via Charge Distributive Network⁴¹ and nervous system interactions) by use of a

⁴⁰ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3898692/>

⁴¹

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330117614_Charge_Distribution_Networks_CDN_as_Meridians_Utilizing_conductivity_as_replacement_%27structure%27_for_meridians_comparison_with_neural_muscular_and_fascial_models

pendulum, as is frequently done in alternative medicine clinics... cannot this data exist in an “akashic field?”

The answer is a fat *maybe*, and *maybe* this is useful, and maybe not. There are some gamification experiments which have yielded stupendous results, and geniuses have been found outside their own fields from the least likely places. People who have not been funneled by culture, society, or educational systems (all forms of MIMS) into these most prized niches. Tall people have become bellhops and fry cooks, and big people insurance agents. There is no reason to think that there aren't some folks with incredible gifts that are not in use at this very moment which could increase “Human Momentum”⁴² by many thousand fold, if they were (with their permission and hearts' interest) put into the right position overnight! What need would there be for AI or robotization? In fact, the entire obsession with efficiency and eliminating jobs would be over, and people could “live the good life” after all and focus on the things they most need, and want: spirituality, family, sex, love, money, and leisure or entertainment. That's really what every adult wants, they just don't say it that way. No one wants to be a “housewife” or “stay at home dad” per se, they want the above things, but they are afraid to lose one or another of them if they don't participate in the mad monkey operation we have evolved, unscientifically, thus far.

Change Theory

Therefore we come, at last, to the Change Theory:

- ❖ The use of data and even dæthereal mechanics.
- ❖ To enhance an OR or DA application.
- ❖ To help increase adherence to the Changes via the five phase options listed previously.
- ❖ To enhance the likelihood of success and reduce the rate of failure or catastrophe.
- ❖ And improve human life, the planet, and solve problems in ways that also improve life and the planet, instead of anti-MIMSically destroying it.

If we are able to tap into secret stores of data and informational energy, which may in fact move faster than light (FTL), or provide us untold SPACER⁴³ and other values, like power, business, economics, etc., all the better. If we are also able to do this in a creative manner, and scale it, it seems potentially likely to create automated systems that reduce impedance and flow, and to provide maximal enriching for minimal struggle and suffering. But to be MIMSical, it must be humanistic and ethical. Or else it will not conform to previous human evolution. This has been covered somewhat in the aforementioned work and in a work on the “New Religion”⁴⁴ (pre-MIMS paper). Nevertheless, consider the following analogy to understand the idea.

A carpenter can carve, and from his mind create a tree house for one child (and friends). This tree is conformed to and cannot be chosen (that's life). However, an architect can use CAD⁴⁵ software to make the tree house. An engineer can make a CAD program and a software

⁴² <https://aetherwizard.com/tesla/Articles/ProblemOfIncreasingHumanEnergy.pdf>

⁴³ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/spacers>

⁴⁴

https://www.academia.edu/38206009/Parameterization_of_New_Religion_utilizing_EP EMC_and_Western_Humanistic_Egalitarianism_as_a_guide

⁴⁵ Computer Aided Design

EPEMC :: Philosophy
Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

engineer can work with said engineer and make an AI⁴⁶ that makes CAD *instances*. Then those can be procedurally generated to either conform to any shape tree, or uniformly to repeat trees (pre-fabricated). Pre-engineered designs could, however, enable the scale to create any size house, and theoretically a biological engineer could manufacture a system that builds high-growth trees, and then works with the AI-CAD P.G. software. Furthermore, if that biological engineer works with a housing and social-systems developer, or civil engineer (etc.) then pre-planned vertical and horizontal growths could be planned that took into account traffic, power, water, and food systems, and entire cities could be grown, with the wood for the tree houses (good to avoid burglars and animals) as well as types of food in the trees could be planned and grown in large warehouse centers. What's more is that the æther or SCS, perhaps one and the same, could be harnessed - or some other "True Green Energy" (TGE)⁴⁷ for the manufacturing center. The tree-neighborhood could be grown on top of multistory, interlaced clonal redwood/sequoia foundations with dispersed clonal aspens. The benefit being clean air, water production atop of the forest⁴⁸, and room for cleansing and pruning robots and landscapers.

The limit is not the ability, but only the mindset.

AI and Analog Computation to Simulate Quantum Fluctuations in the PPPC

The Next^{Next} level of this is not yet achieved, only the Next level! Yes, that sounds boastful, but it is a fact. This is all possible in a Phase1 of Stage 1 human civilization⁴⁹ as we head into Phase 2⁵⁰! In fact, it is depressing so few people think this way. The aforementioned billionaire genius with Aspergers spends his \$45 billion on a toxic (but unfortunately important) anti-MIMSical "social media" website, instead of these and similar ideas. What's the use of all that Potential, if he just wants to leave Planet Earth? I, for one, am disappointed. Of course we don't tell the woke mobsters that, or they might think normal people agree with insane proposals to limit free speech. No, we marginalize that insanity to buy time for movement forward in **real sectors**.

Therefore, let us assume Quantum AI Supremacy (QAIS) has been achieved and is sustainable and not an arms race/anti-MIMS end of modern civilization and human intelligence (enslavement to the AI Beast, aliens, Ub3r-Hitler⁵¹, Skynet etc.) Let us assume 100% positive latency of said QAIS, against all present evidence of the Data companies and social media conglomerates, and all evidence of groupthink horrific experiments, conspiracy facts, and BORG-like hive-mind or mob mentalities. Let's not assume the human psyche slashes and burns but makes a "Jetsons" future! Let's dream "Star Trek" again, and "Data" is our friend and not our "Ash" like enemy!

⁴⁶ Artificial Intelligence

⁴⁷ https://www.academia.edu/62757621/Conquering_the_Solar_System, pp. 17-18

⁴⁸ Redwoods create their own weather!

⁴⁹ CtSS, *Ibid.*, pp. 69-75

⁵⁰ *Ibid.* pp. 76-88

⁵¹ "Batman: Zero Lima Force," Chapter 21, Sf. R. Careaga (not yet published)

Table 1 - AI Robots/Androids, date comparison

<p>Rosey - 1962</p>	<p>Data - 1986</p>	<p>Ash - 1979</p>
<p>Sarcastic, family-oriented, humanlike</p>	<p>Analytical, loyal, near-human</p>	<p>Human, cold, single-minded</p>

Figures 2 - 4; credit: google images/wiki

In such a scenario, might it not be wise to think about **all the missing dæther** in digitization? When we digitize (audio, for example), we sample the reality - the analog - and we turn it from smooth into rough. We limit it. What is missing in this smoothness is that which makes reality more real than our eyes or HDTV's can detect and project. There is a quality or dimension added by other sense beyond eyesight, because there is something sound and touch and smell and taste cover that is not found in the graininess of our gaze. That multi-overlay is not a mistake of evolution or God. Then, consider the missing three senses! We are, in fact, far more interesting than the digital verse.

So, it stands to reason that there might also be quantum fluctuations in the PPPC⁵² which are not detectable by the above AI-CAD_CT ready program, which need to be. Think about it. How many times have we regretted an action and *known* in our hearts something else would be better? And after that, how many times have we also now known how it would be better, because what is or should be is just out of reach of our senses and intellect? So much so, that we ache or itch for the solution set. It's maddening. These slight "jiggles" in the PPPC come from infinite possibilities, very high potentiality in some of those, and certainly a great interest in increasing their probabilities!

Procedurally Generated AI meets Proof of Power

Already mentioned is the P.G. + QAIS scenario, now proposed to be modulated (somehow, mathematicians: get to work!) by Change Theory. So where do we see some major Proof of Power? Where do we see how "the rubber meets the road"?

We see it, right now, unfortunately where OR started: military applications. We see a continual increase in funding and via the alchemical idea of "strike the iron til it's hot": 'value' of the "War Economy." The concept of the War Economy, an antithetical enemy of Dual Layer Economics, was proposed in "Ghost in the Shell" (SAC_2045)⁵³, a work of science fiction. But it

⁵² Possibility-Potentiality-Probability Cloud, https://www.academia.edu/50912946/FAQ_EPEMC_MIMS

⁵³ Technically "Sustainable War"

EPEMC :: Philosophy
Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

describes very accurately the current likely outcome of human endeavors. So much so that the author was able to publish “To Loot a Burning House”⁵⁴ one week before Russia invaded Ukraine!

Figure 5 - “To Loot a Burning House”; credit: author

Therefore faster than the author could warn about WW3.0 to a massive audience, World War 3 was begun by the New World Order and New Axis elites⁵⁵. How sad, and what a terrible way to end the liberalization era, with the closing off of space and potential killing of SPACERization.

Nevertheless, war and military efforts still continue to this day, and we see now that the author is predicting that P.G. and QAIS will begin to rear its head. Meanwhile social AI appears to be getting dumber, and more attuned to the “mass formed psychosis”, either by design, or asymmetric attack (Chussia? Aliens? Big Data’s socialist fervor? AI Overlord itself? Satan??? LEGION?⁵⁶).

So what is the proof of power? Work over time *or* potential times current is our best definition. The issue, therefore, is can this PG-QAIS work? The author, and many in the Pulse think tank have their doubts. So we have no answer. Turing seemed to think so. Others say that AI will never be really conscious. Google’s DeepMind says it is about to be, but that could be nothing more than publicity stunts for more War Economy contracts. The Christians have taken to believing all of this is proof of Revelations. That’s ironic as the Left (generally more atheist) seems to want to create nuclear holocaust since their “daddies” of Big Social Media and Mainstream Media told them they need it. It’s very humorous on the one hand to suddenly love Nazis in the Ukraine, but on the other hand not humorous at all. It is a serious threat, and should be taken seriously. It won’t be by Congress - the author tried to warn them in January 2019 and nothing was done. Probably because the Congressman is owned wholly or partially by Chussia⁵⁷. Nevertheless, the end result is that it isn’t clear that proof of power is coming out of anything truly creative anytime soon. Therefore, the author is **highly skeptical** of the effort to create Stage 2 civilization without addressing Stage 1’s three critical phases of development and getting away from poor STEMM issues:

- Scientism instead of science
- Technocracy
- Engineering via reaction instead of pro-action
- Mathemagicks
- Medicine via poison, barbarism, and to feed the Human Flesh Industry “fresh fetal cells”⁵⁸

⁵⁴ <https://www.amazon.com/Loot-Burning-House-Ramon-Careaga/dp/1643384368>

⁵⁵ https://www.academia.edu/51022722/Winning_the_New_Cold_War_World_War_3

⁵⁶ As the author wrote this, his “right heart” - the emotional energy side - seized with a fit of pain. He wasn’t breathing!

⁵⁷ China-Russia Alliance (via petro-Yuan)

⁵⁸ https://www.academia.edu/78671704/POS_1_01_No_Roe_v_Wade_is_not_Libertarian ,pp.9-10

EPEMC :: Philosophy
Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

Without these dealt with, the author has (an admittedly religious belief or even hope) that mankind *cannot* harvest the Æther, without fixing these issues. And he also believes that only the *L* power (The Lord) and Change Theory will enable this. That is his bias. It is an extraordinary claim in science, but not mytho-historically. This is something known by all cultures *except our own hedonistic one*, which may have become corrupted by misuse, misapplication, and misunderstanding (or reverse engineering by shadowy adversaries) of the Force itself. I.e.: since the late 1800s and especially since Hitler (of all people) was first broadcasted into space. It cannot be good, either, to be broadcasting Satanic imagery, and barbarism, as well as xenophobia (literally, of extraterrestrials) and manufacturing “weapons of the gods”⁵⁹ which are aimed at ourselves and not even those we threaten. When the author says broadcast, he means literally cable/satellite TV signals and movies going forward (and backward?) in time. Pushing The Force might not even be the right method to make power. Charging money (a *dæther*?) for it might be sacrilegious, for all we know. The Internet might be the anti-Christ. We have no stinking clue about anything.

New QED+EHD

The first quantum electrodynamic model⁶⁰ was laid out by Feynman⁶¹ et al. They only utilized one dimension of electrical formulae, and three dimensions of magnetism. However, in the era of supercomputing the time is ripe to revisit that, perhaps an AI, and re-do all of QED in a complete manner, with eddy currents and surface currents added. R. Distinti⁶² has provided both a vector form of Maxwell/Heaviside and a Votrix Algebra⁶³ to enable it, as well as solved the riddle of the imaginary number, in matrix form. The issue, therefore, is simply doing it. But by solving this, we may begin to understand:

- ❖ The sun’s rotating current sheets give us alternation of weather and even sensation or psychiatric experience.
- ❖ How the proton density more precisely affects our CDN and causes pain and psychological torment.
- ❖ How these are modulated with the Earth’s transformer⁶⁴ rotation and causes the Changes to affect us.

Furthermore there is a little known, young, field called electrohydrodynamics, which seeks to replicate the ideas within magnetohydrodynamics⁶⁵, but obviously with Maxwell’s equations. It is young but powerful, and although not widely known or utilized, the author believes a marriage of it with MHD is essential and imminent. It may very well be the key to unlocking the new QED and New Electromagnetic paradigm, as Distinti puts it, and finally to enabling us to model the Force, field aligned or not, force-free field aligned or not, etc. The

⁵⁹ https://www.academia.edu/69494984/Plasmaglyphs_Part_4 , pp. 127

⁶⁰ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/quantum/qed>

⁶¹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/giants-of-eu-history>

⁶² <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/other-eu/r-distinti>

⁶³ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TSPsi3c_nh8&list=PL2fbwSsQ2zIVFTOb1FOPnqNMLsuWgFXHb

⁶⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Q355Haapq-0>

⁶⁵ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/mag-universe/mhd>

entire PEM. The one caution is that this will probably only work out if there is a strong relational study between the EM theoreticians and high energy plasma (HEP) physicists!

What intrigues the author about all of this is the possibility, maybe even increasing, probability of making a wide study of the Changes and the application of Change Theory (a philosophy) back into the PEMC. Think of it this way: PEMC > EPEMC > MIMS > Change Theory (also from China) > PEMC. A full circle back towards utilization of the Æther in this realistic manner.

Simulating Natural Systems with Enhanced Mechanics, and QEHD

Assume for a moment that the author is correct about the QEHD emerging, and assume it has already married MHD! Assume, at least impending if not total merger of the Electroweak and Strong forces under a SAM⁶⁶ v 2.0 as discussed elsewhere in an EPEMC article.

What could be done with this knowledge? Weather seems the most likely choice, because the marriage of space-weather with weather, as documented by B. Davidson is showing this pretty strongly⁶⁷. This strong coherence and merger indicates that electrogeology is likely also to fall in, perhaps even his concept of “Earth Spots.”⁶⁸ But, what else can be done?

Biological systems, and figuring out not only why spiders make certain web shapes, or why animals migrate in certain ways, but even how they are likely to swarm, flee humans and ships, breed, or as the case may be be unable to breed because of some form of human pollution or EM changes to the Earth (causing a general “Climate Change”⁶⁹).

The point is that each of these scenarios is probably only the tip of the iceberg when it comes to dealing with EM effects and changes on this planet, and their ramification on us, or vice versa. There might be a non-linear dynamical means by which Changes alter us, and we alter Changes; and the sum causal relationship to that might be incalculable. It might be “Heaven” doesn’t want us to have this knowledge, or perhaps aliens, or perhaps we don’t deserve and cannot handle it. It is equally possible that it would give us bad impressions from wrong interpretations, or that spirituality is unmodelable with math and therefore would lead us to a polarizing destruction of self and planet. It might be that it also fixes issues almost as well as “getting God” and “going backwards” or “inwards” or “seeking enlightenment.” Etc.

It might be the ultimate Pandora’s Box. Or it might be one of those things we do and then later wonder why it wasn’t done before. It might be that we cannot handle the guilt or shame of having allowed barbarism to continue, or conversely, we might discover why we and chimpanzees and animals are barbaric and that our attempts to purify and squeeze all sin out are wasted efforts. That Nature prefers and selects for dominance those that are full of “evil.” It might be that the situation is untenable, that war is inevitable, or that we go to fight the wars

⁶⁶ Structured Atomic Model

⁶⁷ “Weatherman’s Guide to the Sun,” B. Davidson; also the SuspiciousObservers channel

⁶⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4BvuDOnAfJs>

⁶⁹ https://www.academia.edu/36753643/Our_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Sky_Application_of_Hollow_Expanding_Growing_Electromagnetic_Earth_Hypothesis_with_particular_respect_to_the_Earths_Atmosphere_starting_from_the_Lithosphere_and_ascending_Altitude

within and without and discover that laughter or compassion overrides all these feelings with rationalism, and all the feelings override the facts of horror and destruction and we need mere humility. Perhaps the Tao would humble us, finally, or ultimately. Or perhaps the angels and aliens would come and destroy us for knowing this power, or we would destroy them by using it, and become devils ourselves. But it seems, to the author at least, that knowing the Changes has helped individuals for a long time. Knowing them, for fact, therefore could not necessarily be an evil. And yet, mayhaps the author is struck dead by the end of this paper for nearly supplying Heaven's Secrets. Only time will tell. We do know that "Heaven" of a sort gives responses.

We saw what happened to the mural of George Floyd⁷⁰ people worshiped: his face was hit with a 'stray' lightning bolt⁷¹. He was buried in gold like a pharaoh⁷², but he was a criminal and drug abuser. So a society that doesn't observe some mode of decorum appears manifestly doomed to aggravate the ire of the Force. But how that manifests in the Changes is not clear, at all. It *seems* nukes will fly any day now. But it might be a comet or asteroid, or solar CME (X-20 class). We really have no grasp, and we pretend to be in control. We really are decidedly *not* in control. We know nothing, are nothing, and yet that (God-Truth) makes us something. And there is a "course of work"⁷³ and "a firing process."⁷⁴ But knowing that process is difficult.

Applying Change Theory as an Operations Research using QEHD

Back to the realm of reality, how will OR_CT affect and be affected by QEHD? The short answer is, "we don't know." Of course. This is where the paper gets into pure Science Fiction. First that the assumptions hold, and then that Change Theory is useful, and that it is applicable to or as an Operations Research (a known MIMS of inestimable value). Could it be that this information will lead to a revolution of the world via project management? Is this what finally lets us leave Stage 1 society behind, as we get truly serious about a long term plan to Conquer the Solar System? Or maybe it simply modulates our entire society, governments (or gets rid of and replaces government!?), politics, economics, etc.? The bottom line is that we won't know until we try. And we won't try until we observe, question, and ask the *right* questions, based upon some very difficult to see issues (we don't spend much time marveling over the alterations of things, and are easily caught up in momentary feelings).

The author has, like anyone, his own sins, vices, and virtues which are grave and great forces in his life. He has values, beliefs, and paradigms, as well as a background or education. We **all** have a relativistic point of view which is finite, mortal, and highly limited/mostly subjective. Objectivity is hard to find, and a distinct right and wrong eludes people the more the Dark Side spreads, and the mystery of that is quite an issue delving dangerously close to solipsism⁷⁵. However, to ignore these musings on account or discount of the author, his writings,

⁷⁰ P.O.S Theory, Ibid. pp. 24

⁷¹ <https://nypost.com/2021/07/14/george-floyd-mural-collapses-witnesses-blame-lightning/>

⁷²

<https://www.news.com.au/world/north-america/george-floyd-funeral-thousands-queue-to-see-golden-casket-to-pay-respects/news-story/05423091452b0433a8327038ef05cd10>

⁷³ "Taoist I Ching," Liu Yiming

⁷⁴ "Wuzhu Pian"

⁷⁵ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/solipsism>

biases, future or past events, choices, fallibilities, limitations, political leanings, etc. would be a potentially colossal mistake for all of mankind, business, etc.

Conclusions

We must, as a species, have the maturity to seek objectivity and even to understand Change Theory more and more in terms of the flow of Truth, rather than a destination of it. An unfolding Destiny (ming, 明)⁷⁶ process... *Daoing*, as it were... which then brings into awareness that which is readily available at the outset, and yet not seen without effort. The Tao is at the tip of the nose, we are *in* God and with God at all times, but psychologically must make every effort, and the Force is there constantly guiding this interaction. Attaining fortune, making wealth and material richness, receiving power, access, influence, fame, and adulation, etc. are all secondary to our needs for love and acceptance, security in a niche, etc. But mostly, it is secondary to our obtaining that favour we seek, implicitly or subconsciously or overtly, from a higher Source of charge/energy-mass. It might very well be the best - or last - thing we ever do (the author wrote *dao* first). It might be the most consequential step, .. or it might (unlikely enough) be inconsequential. Only by spending some philosophical and scientific rigor upon the subject can we then shape a new Enlightenment, and the author contends, escape the Unlightenment.

We no longer conform to reality... and this is why we are made to suffer as a species. Whether tribes or a Republic or "the commies" are right... well that all needs to be fought out not in wars, nor in vulnerable populations like children, nor in governmental circles where a constant beat of drums for war ever looms. It needs to be fought out in scientific circles with experiments and attempts to carefully and seriously label potential outcomes, knowing that the exact set of circumstances can never repeat. Only by diagnosing a pattern of empirical behavior, billions of times, starting from an assumption that new math might be needed, do we have any hope to garner the wisdom the ancient Chinese had after witnessing the cataclysms... converting it from empirical knowledge into tangible, concrete commandments. Until then the I Ching, Psalms, Proverbs, Tao Te Ching, Sutras, Sufism, and sayings of Jesus might remain our best ways of understanding this slippery facet of reality. What the Taoists termed, "the mysterious pivot" (*lingshu*). How recondite! Yet, the author sees vast stores of energy, money, investment, and future in those things. Now: go do it!

⁷⁶ "Xing-ming Guizhi,"

https://drive.google.com/file/d/0BwoOz_mUBUfuNmlkNmcyNmpnYm8/view?usp=sharing&resourcekey=0-wG3dpQERBLO_OWMdys3X4w

References

1. "On the Membranous Interface of the Material and the Spiritual (from an EPEMC perspective) & Dual/Double Layer Economics... a proposed test of EPEMC's 'metallic' properties: tensile strength, malleability, durability," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/50300514/On_the_Membranous_Interface_of_the_Material_and_the_Spiritual_from_an_EPEMC_perspective_and_Dual_Double_Layer_Economics_a_proposed_test_of_EPEMCs_metallic_properties_tensile_strength_malleability_durability
2. "Explication of the Versatility of the "BigG" diagram in MIMS 1.0," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/53271235/Explication_of_the_Versatility_of_the_Big_G_diagram_in_MIMS_1_0
3. Genesis 1:26
4. "How the West Was Lost: The Transformation of Kentucky From Daniel Boone to Henry Clay," Amazon, Prof. S. Aron, 1996, <https://www.amazon.com/How-West-Was-Lost-Transformation/dp/080185296X/>
5. "MIMS 2.83 - POS Theory," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/77592483/MIMS_2_83_POS_Theory
6. "Sphere," Amazon, M. Crichton, 2011, <https://www.amazon.com/Sphere-Michael-Crichton/dp/0061990558/>
7. "MIMS 2 Applications discussions," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/50804855/MIMS_2_Applications_discussions
8. "Standing Wave," Encyclopedia Britannica" Physics, <https://www.britannica.com/science/standing-wave-physics>
9. Matthew 13
10. "MIMS 2.2.1.1-3 : The Threefold Science," Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1LcH2FypSjI27RZYI8NnxqtXiHq8Ub7KsFrcRIRJ3pRE/edit#heading=h.4w083fuxm8i3>
11. "Magnetic Universe Theory A Top-Down Review of Phases of Magnetic Theory Development, with accompanying historiography and comparison with Unified/Aether Field Theories including EPEMC," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2018, https://www.academia.edu/37439506/Magnetic_Universe_Theory_A_Top_Down_Review_of_Phases_of_Magnetic_Theory_Development_with_accompanying_historiography_and_comparison_with_Unified_Aether_Field_Theories_including_EPEMC
12. "Our Plasma-Electromagnetic Sky Application of Hollow-Expanding-Growing-Electromagnetic Earth Hypothesis with particular respect to the Earth's Atmosphere starting from the Lithosphere and ascending Altitude," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2018, https://www.academia.edu/36753643/Our_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Sky_Application_of_Hollow_Expanding_Growing_Electromagnetic_Earth_Hypothesis_with_particular_respect_to_the_Earths_Atmosphere_starting_from_the_Lithosphere_and_ascending_Altitude
13. "MIMS 2.6.1 : Shi勢 A short look at an ancient multidimensional model." Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/50357891/MIMS_and_Shi
14. "MIMS 2.102 - In pursuit of the Daether," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/67236577/MIMS_2_102_In_pursuit_of_the_Daether
15. "MIMS 2.1.212a - Fibonacci Pressure," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/67387410/MIMS_2_1_212a_Fibonacci_Pressure
16. "MIMS 2.6.2 : Strategy & Dualism," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/51643169/MIMS_2_6_2_Strategy_and_Dualism
17. "The Peer Review Cult "cover-up": Conspiracy Facts the 'fact-checkers' do not want you to know about," Academia, EPEMC: Opinion Editorial, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/74466574/The_Peer_Review_Cult_cover_up_Conspiracy_Facts_the_fact_checkers_do_not_want_you_to_know_about

EPEMC :: Philosophy
Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

18. "Stratospheric Aerosol Injection (SAI) ,"geoengineering monitor.org. 2021, ,
https://www.geoengineeringmonitor.org/2021/02/stratospheric_aerosol_injection/
19. ""Pearl Harbor and the "Back Door to War" Theory," Encyclopedia Britannica, R. Dalleck, 2018,
<https://www.britannica.com/topic/Pearl-Harbor-and-the-back-door-to-war-theory-1688287>
20. "Operations Research History," Encyclopedia Britannica,
<https://www.britannica.com/topic/operations-research/History>
21. "The Origins of OR," Informs.org.:The Institute for Operations Research and the Management Sciences,
<https://www.informs.org/Explore/History-of-O.R.-Excellence/Bibliographies/The-Origins-of-OR>
22. "Game Theory," Wiki, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Game_theory
23. "Queuing Theory," Investopedia, J. Mansa, 2021,
<https://www.investopedia.com/terms/q/queuing-theory.asp#:~:text=Queuing%20theory%20examines%20every%20component,a%20wide%20range%20of%20businesses>
24. "What is Data Analytics?," MastersInDataScience.org., 2022,
<https://www.mastersindata-science.org/learning/what-is-data-analytics/>
25. "MIMS 1.01-.03: Philosophy Integration Self test," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021,
https://www.academia.edu/65563310/MIMS_1_01_03_Philosophy_Integration_Self_test
26. MIMS 2.0, Ibid, pp. 5-6
27. "Original Tao: Inward Training (Nei-yeh) and the Foundations of Taoist Mysticism," Amazon, H. Roth, 2004, <https://www.amazon.com/Original-Tao-Foundations-Mysticism-Translations/dp/0231115652/>
28. "The Akashic Records: Origins and Relation to Western Concepts," Central European Journal of Contemporary Religion, A. Nash, 2020, https://karolinum.cz/data/clanek/8423/CEJCR_3_2_0109.pdf
29. "MIMS: Aether Flow & Business Circuit Theory," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022,
https://www.academia.edu/76140647/MIMS_Aether_Flow_and_Business_Circuit_Theory
30. "What We Know Currently about Mirror Neurons," Current Biology, J.M. Kilner & R.N. Lemon, 2013,
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3898692/>
31. "Charge Distribution Networks (CDN) as Meridians Utilizing conductivity as replacement 'structure' for meridians; comparison with neural, muscular, and fascial models," Research Gate, Sf. R. Careaga, 2019,
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330117614_Charge_Distribution_Networks_CDN_as_Meridians_Utilizing_conductivity_as_replacement_%27structure%27_for_meridians_comparison_with_neural_muscular_and_fascial_models
32. "The Problem of Increasing Human Energy with Special References to the Harnessing of the Sun's Energy," Century Magazine, N. Tesla, 1900,
<https://aetherwizard.com/tesla/Articles/ProblemOfIncreasingHumanEnergy.pdf>
33. "SPACERS, LLC - "are you a spacer, What's in A Name ?" (EPEMC) Gateway, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021,
<https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/spacers>
34. "Parameterization of New Religion utilizing EPEMC and Western Humanistic Egalitarianism as a guide," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2019,
https://www.academia.edu/38206009/Parameterization_of_New_Religion_utilizing_EPEMC_and_Western_Humanistic_Egalitarianism_as_a_guide
35. "Conquering the Solar System," (pp. 17-18,) Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021,
https://www.academia.edu/62757621/Conquering_the_Solar_System
36. "Batman: Zero Lima Force," Chapter 21, Sf. R. Careaga (not yet published)
37. "FAQ: (EPEMC) MIMS Vers 1," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021,
https://www.academia.edu/50912946/FAQ_EP EMC_MIMS
38. "To Loot a Burning House," Amazon, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022,
<https://www.amazon.com/Loot-Burning-House-Ramon-Careaga/dp/1643384368>
39. "Winning the New Cold War & World War 3.0," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021,
https://www.academia.edu/51022722/Winning_the_New_Cold_War_World_War_3
40. "POS 1.01 No, Roe v Wade is not Libertarian, (pp.9-10)
41. POS: Opinion: Editorial Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022,
https://www.academia.edu/78671704/POS_1_01_No_Roe_v_Wade_is_not_Libertarian
42. "Plasmaglyphs Part 4 (pp. 127) ," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga,
https://www.academia.edu/69494984/Plasmaglyphs_Part_4

EPEMC :: Philosophy
Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

43. "U VA01 00: Vortrix Algebra Introduction," Youtube, R. Distini, 2018, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TSPsi3c_nh8&list=PL2fbwSsQ2zIVFTOb1FOPnqNMI_suWgFXHb
44. "Bruce Leybourne: Geometry of Earth's Endogenous Electrical Energy -- Geophysical Evidence EU2016," Youtube, Thunderbolts Project, 2018, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Q355Haapq-0&t=474s>
45. "Weatherman's Guide to the Sun," B. Davidson; also the SuspiciousObservers channel
46. "Sunspots, Solar Forcing Confirmations, Special Video | S0 News," Youtube, SuspiciousObservers, 2021, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4BvuDOnAfJs>
47. "Our Plasma-Electromagnetic Sky Application of Hollow-Expanding-Growing-Electromagnetic Earth Hypothesis with particular respect to the Earth's Atmosphere starting from the Lithosphere and ascending Altitude," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2018,
48. https://www.academia.edu/36753643/Our_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Sky_Application_of_Hollow_Expanding_Growing_Electromagnetic_Earth_Hypothesis_with_particular_respect_to_the_Earths_Atmosphere_starting_from_the_Lithosphere_and_ascending_Altitude
49. "Witnesses claim lightning destroyed George Floyd mural in Ohio," New York Post, J. R. Miller, 2021, <https://nypost.com/2021/07/14/george-floyd-mural-collapses-witnesses-blame-lightning/>
50. "George Floyd funeral: Thousands queue to see golden casket to pay respects," Nationwide News Pty Ltd, 2020, <https://www.news.com.au/world/north-america/george-floyd-funeral-thousands-queue-to-see-golden-casket-to-pay-respects/news-story/05423091452b0433a8327038ef05cd10>
51. "Taoist I Ching," Liu Yimin
52. "Wuzhu Pian"
53. "Definition of solipsism," Merriam-Webster, <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/solipsism>
54. "Xing-ming Guizhi, Integrating Inner Alchemy into Late Ming Cultural History: A Contextualization and Annotated Translation of Principles of the Innate Disposition, A thesis submitted to the Graduate School of the University of Colorado, D. B. Rose, 2009, https://drive.google.com/file/d/0BwoOz_mUBUfuNmIkNmcyNmpnYm8/view?resourcekey=0-wG3dpQERBLO_OWMDys3X4w